

DV	Outcome	Type	Comparison (A vs. B)	M.Diff.	SE	<i>p</i>
Effectiveness	Accepted	Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Tenant Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Tenant Initiated)	1.17	0.26	< .001
		Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Tenant Initiated) vs. Monetary Compensation (Host Initiated)	0.30	0.24	.602
		Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Tenant Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Host Initiated)	1.32	0.27	< .001
		Strategy	Physical Adjustment (Tenant Initiated) vs. Monetary Compensation (Host Initiated)	-0.87	0.25	.003
		Strategy	Physical Adjustment (Tenant Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Host Initiated)	0.14	0.26	.942
		Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Host Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Host Initiated)	1.02	0.27	< .001
		Device	Driveway camera vs. Video conferencing device for TVs	-1.27	0.23	< .001
		Device	Driveway camera vs. Smart display device	-1.54	0.24	< .001
		Device	Video conferencing device for TVs vs. Smart display device	-0.28	0.20	.365
	Declined	Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Tenant Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Tenant Initiated)	0.88	0.25	.002
		Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Tenant Initiated) vs. Monetary Compensation (Host Initiated)	0.64	0.25	.044
		Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Tenant Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Host Initiated)	1.32	0.26	< .001
		Strategy	Physical Adjustment (Tenant Initiated) vs. Monetary Compensation (Host Initiated)	-0.24	0.23	.736
		Strategy	Physical Adjustment (Tenant Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Host Initiated)	0.43	0.24	.265
		Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Host Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Host Initiated)	0.67	0.24	.025
		Device	Driveway camera vs. Video conferencing device for TVs	-0.84	0.21	< .001
		Device	Driveway camera vs. Smart display device	-0.99	0.21	< .001
		Device	Video conferencing device for TVs vs. Smart display device	-0.15	0.21	.738
Practicality	Accepted	Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Tenant Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Tenant Initiated)	0.82	0.26	.009
		Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Tenant Initiated) vs. Monetary Compensation (Host Initiated)	0.40	0.25	.373
		Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Tenant Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Host Initiated)	0.57	0.26	.127
		Strategy	Physical Adjustment (Tenant Initiated) vs. Monetary Compensation (Host Initiated)	-0.41	0.26	.385
		Strategy	Physical Adjustment (Tenant Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Host Initiated)	-0.25	0.26	.790
		Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Host Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Host Initiated)	0.17	0.26	.918
		Device	Driveway camera vs. Video conferencing device for TVs	-0.51	0.23	.065
		Device	Driveway camera vs. Smart display device	-0.83	0.23	< .001
		Device	Video conferencing device for TVs vs. Smart display device	-0.32	0.22	.316
	Declined	Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Tenant Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Tenant Initiated)	0.48	0.27	.278
		Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Tenant Initiated) vs. Monetary Compensation (Host Initiated)	0.64	0.27	.080
		Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Tenant Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Host Initiated)	0.73	0.27	.033
		Strategy	Physical Adjustment (Tenant Initiated) vs. Monetary Compensation (Host Initiated)	0.16	0.26	.932
		Strategy	Physical Adjustment (Tenant Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Host Initiated)	0.25	0.27	.794
		Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Host Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Host Initiated)	0.09	0.27	.987

DV	Outcome	Type	Comparison (A vs. B)	M. Diff.	SE	<i>p</i>
		Device	Driveway camera vs. Video conferencing device for TVs	-0.24	0.23	.553
		Device	Driveway camera vs. Smart display device	-0.54	0.22	.045
		Device	Video conferencing device for TVs vs. Smart display device	-0.30	0.22	.369
Willingness	Accepted	Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Tenant Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Tenant Initiated)	1.07	0.25	< .001
		Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Tenant Initiated) vs. Monetary Compensation (Host Initiated)	0.52	0.24	.124
		Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Tenant Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Host Initiated)	1.28	0.26	< .001
		Strategy	Physical Adjustment (Tenant Initiated) vs. Monetary Compensation (Host Initiated)	-0.55	0.24	.110
		Strategy	Physical Adjustment (Tenant Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Host Initiated)	0.21	0.25	.834
		Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Host Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Host Initiated)	0.76	0.25	.015
		Device	Driveway camera vs. Video conferencing device for TVs	-0.58	0.22	.019
		Device	Driveway camera vs. Smart display device	-0.90	0.22	< .001
		Device	Video conferencing device for TVs vs. Smart display device	-0.32	0.21	.256
	Declined	Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Tenant Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Tenant Initiated)	0.48	0.26	.255
		Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Tenant Initiated) vs. Monetary Compensation (Host Initiated)	0.36	0.25	.485
		Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Tenant Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Host Initiated)	0.92	0.26	.002
		Strategy	Physical Adjustment (Tenant Initiated) vs. Monetary Compensation (Host Initiated)	-0.12	0.25	.965
		Strategy	Physical Adjustment (Tenant Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Host Initiated)	0.44	0.26	.323
		Strategy	Monetary Compensation (Host Initiated) vs. Physical Adjustment (Host Initiated)	0.56	0.26	.131
		Device	Driveway camera vs. Video conferencing device for TVs	-0.19	0.22	.669
		Device	Driveway camera vs. Smart display device	-0.16	0.22	.737
		Device	Video conferencing device for TVs vs. Smart display device	0.03	0.22	.992

Note. Tukey-adjusted pairwise comparisons from the stratified-by-outcome CLMMs, reported as estimated directly by the model. Negative mean differences indicate the first-listed condition was more favorable. The main text reports the same comparisons with reversed signs (physical/driveway as the reference) for readability.